

Open Science Office Impact Report 2021-2023 (Summary)

Impact Report 2021–2023

Open Science Office of the University of Mannheim

Report compiled by
David Philip Morgan Philipp Zumstein

Last modified: October 20, 2023

Table of contents

Table of contents

1 Introduction	
2 Uptake and Trends of Open Science	
2.1 Political Context	
2.2 Research Culture	
3 Strategic Developments at the University of Mannheim	
4 Impact Assessment	
4.1 Open Science Training and Education	
4.1.1 Key Statistics	
4.1.2 Scope	
4.1.3 Target Audience	
4.1.4 Participants' Evaluation	
4.1.5 Website and Materials	
4.1.6 Other Points	
4.2 Open Science Support Services	
4.2.1 Open Science Consultation Services	
4.2.2 Open Science Grants	
4.3 Networking and Visibility	
4.3.1 Networking within the University	
4.3.2 Networking Regionally, Nationally and Internationally	
4.3.3 Organization of Public Events	
4.3.4 Presentations of the Open Science Office at National and International Events	
4.4 Management Summary	
5 Expenditure Report	
5.1 Financial Resources	
5.2 Personnel Resources	
6 Future Directions	
Data Availability Statement	
7 Appendix	
7.1 Open Science Timeline for the University of Mannheim	
7.2 Course Structure of the Mannheim Master in Social Data Science	
7.3 Questionnaire of the Participants' Evaluation from the Open Science Seminar	

1 Introduction

Open Science as a collective term includes opening up the end stages of research (e.g. Open Access for publications, open data and research software) as well as principles of transparent and replicable research (e.g. via pre-registration, reproducible workflows). Further aspects of Open Science such as Citizen Science, Third Mission or Open Educational Resources (OER) are also increasing in importance and have an impact on society, where the research process and what is learned from research is opened up to the public. The purpose of the Open Science Office is to anchor Open Science institutionally at the University of Mannheim and have a central contact point for Open Science requests within the university. Additionally, expanding Open Science support and infrastructure for researchers institutionally, the Open Science Office aims to increase the attractiveness of the University of Mannheim as a research location, respond to the increasing demands of third-party funders in this field and showcase our commitment to transparency and reproducibility in the research process.

On 10.09.2020 the research council unanimously recommended the establishment of an Open Science Office at the university and its funding for three years from the research fund. The rectorate then followed this recommendation on 20.09.2020 and mandated the library with the implementation of an Open Science Office. The new position of an Open Science Officer was filled by February 2021 and then again in May 2022 with a gap of 4 months in-between. The Open Science Office is operationally led by the Open Access representative and integrated with the library. Strategically the Open Science Office is advised by a newly established Open Science council since 2021. This board consists of all the members of the research council and three additional experts mostly from outside the university. The board meets at least yearly during the research council meeting and is led by the vice-president for research.

After the initial funding of three years, it was agreed that an evaluation process will take place to decide whether the Open Science Office should be made permanent. The following report is part of this process and presents the impact of the Open Science Office since 2021. The self-evaluation is based on three core dimensions that were agreed upon by the Rectorate on 30.06.2021 following the recommendation of the Research Council:

1. Open Science Training and Education
2. Open Science Translating and Funding
3. Networking and Visibility

Based on the reported impact of these dimensions in this impact report, the Open Science Council will make a recommendation on whether the Open Science Office should be made permanent. The final decision about the continuation of funding for the Open Science Office then needs to be made by the rectorate.

Figure 1: Organization of the Open Science Office and the parties involved at the University of Mannheim

2 Uptake and Trends of Open Science

2.1 Political Context

The topic of Open Science has been prominent on the EU's political agenda for years. In recent years there are more and more top-down political activities around Open Science. In 2021, UNESCO published its Recommendation on Open Science¹ and Open Science became part of the latest communiqué of the G7 Science and Technology Ministers² in May 2023.

Consolidating such global approaches, national plans for Open Science have emerged in The Netherlands³, France⁴, Italy⁵, Ireland⁶, and Ukraine⁷ (possibly more as well) and beyond Europe. In the US, the White House — joined by 10 federal agencies, a coalition of more than 85 universities, and other organizations — declared 2023 to be a Year of Open Science⁸ to spark change and inspire Open Science engagement through events and activities. Germany has also followed suit, and in 2021 the Koalitionsvertrag⁹ also mentioned Open Science more broadly besides Open Access.

These political shifts reflect an increased weight of importance on opening up science to the public. In addition, broad and generally accessible communication of scientific research findings

¹<https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>
²https://www.ec.europa.eu/press/koenigshofer/g7_2023/230513_g7_communique.pdf
³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767>
⁴<https://www.openaccess.eu/news/national-plan-for-open-science-published-by-the-mur/>
⁵<https://researchitaly.univ-gov.it/en/2022/07/15/national-plan-for-open-science-published-by-the-mur/>
⁶<https://doi.org/10.7446/OJLI.65p0222>
⁷<https://www.kmu.gov.ua/en/news/ukraina-priyomlas-do-krajin-ino-shcho-maita-antivobrozhny-plan-rezultatni-pylytytyo-vidkryto-mayky>
⁸<https://open-science.gov/>
⁹<https://open-access.network/services/news/artikel/koalitionsvertrag-2021-open-access-als-standard>

Dr. David Philip Morgan and Dr. Philipp Zumstein
University of Mannheim, Open Science Office

Where do we stand?

- ✓ 09.2020, **establishment of the Open Science Office** for three years based on the recommendation by the research council and decision by the rectorate
- ✓ 30.06.2021, rectorate agreed on the **evaluation dimensions**
- ✓ 11.2022, **interim report**, addressing the evaluation dimensions, provided to Open Science Council who provided some feedback, but **requested no changes to the portfolio** of the Open Science Office
- ✓ 07.2023, **Structure and Development Plan (SteP)** confirms that the University of Mannheim is committed to the further development of the Open Science culture as well as the intention to make the Open Science Office permanent in 2024 if the evaluation is successful.

Today: Evaluation and recommendation of the permanency of the Open Science Office using the Impact Report against the agreed upon dimensions

Evaluation Dimension of the Open Science Office

Training & Education

Support & Services

Networking & Visibility

Training and Education

Impact Report, Section 4.1

Training and Education

Dimension Criteria

Number, duration, scope + evaluation of educational offers

Reaching target groups + entire spectrum of subjects

Provision of Open Science Content

Costs for Open Science Conferences for researchers

The Open Science Office has provided **over 70 hours** of training and educational opportunities **to almost 600 individuals since 2021:**

Some researchers now use Open Science Practices as a result of the Open Science Seminars

Training and Education

Dimension Criteria

**Number, duration,
scope + evaluation of
educational offers**

Reaching target groups
+ entire spectrum of
subjects

Provision of Open
Science Content

Costs for Open Science
Conferences for
researchers

Individuals who participated in the Open Science Seminars were surveyed about their impressions of the series:

Training and Education

Dimension Criteria

Number, duration,
scope and evaluation
of educational offers

**Reaching target groups
+ entire spectrum of
subjects**

Provision of Open
Science Content

Costs for Open Science
Conferences for
researchers

Open Science is a **cross-cutting interdisciplinary topic** which lends itself **to target a broad range of groups and subjects:**

1. Administrative employees, librarians, and research services (e.g., Division I) account for 10% of all training provided
2. The annual Open Science Day was open to a mixture of audiences (e.g., public, researchers, administrative)
3. > 80% of opportunities were aimed at and attended by researchers at the University of Mannheim

Training and Education

Dimension Criteria

Number, duration,
scope and evaluation
of educational offers

Reaching target groups
+ entire spectrum of
subjects

Provision of Open
Science Content

Costs for Open Science
Conferences for
researchers

Pre-Registration and Data Repository Practices in Business and Marketing Research

Prof. Dr. Sabine Kuester | Chair of Marketing & Innovation

Open Science Day 2023
12 October 2023

Open Data in the Study of Ancient History

MELANIE MEAKER
LEHRSTUHL FÜR ALTE GESCHICHTE
UNIVERSITÄT MANNHEIM

Research Transparency and the Diversity of Qualitative Research

Sebastian Karcher, QDR
Mannheim University, Open Science Office
May 9, 2023

Data and Replication Policies in Economics

Arthur Seibold (University of Mannheim)

Open Science Day, Mannheim, 12 October 2023

Open Science Day 2022

Artificial Intelligence, Information Processing and Dissemination

Kerstin Bauer (Leibniz Institute for Economic Research IZA)
Florian Ertzig (Business School, University of Mannheim)
Harmut Hoehle (Business School, University of Mannheim)

October 2022

Publikationsservices und Forschungsunterstützung

Philipp Zumstein, Jorge Murcia, Sylvia Hulin
2022-05-06, Romanisches Institut

Training and Education

Dimension Criteria

Number, duration, scope and evaluation of educational offers

Reaching target groups + entire spectrum of subjects

Provision of Open Science Content

Costs for Open Science Conferences for researchers

Open Science content is provided to researchers **on the Open Science Office Website:**

Open Science Office

The Open Science Office of the University of Mannheim was established in February 2021. It is linked to the University Library and is a point of contact for everything related to Open Science.

Supporting and Training Researchers

The Open Science Office supports researchers at all career stages and from all disciplines. We offer *Open Science Checks* to examine each researchers' potential and support the implementation of Open Science techniques into their research. Via *training* in various formats as well as our upcoming *website*, information on Open Science can be obtained. *Funding* is provided for Open Science research projects (*Open Science Grants*) and can be applied for conference visits or research stays that focus on Open Science.

39 presentations are publicly available online

Support and Services

Support and Services

Dimension Criteria

Number of consultations including target groups and thematic scope

Satisfaction of researchers with consultations

Outcomes and success of Open Science Grants, outcomes and feedback

The Open Science Office **has provided over 60 Open Science consultations since the beginning of 2022**, supporting researchers at the university with integrating Open Science into their research:

		Faculty	No.
Career Level	No.	Law	1
Professor	17	Economics	1
Junior Prof.	2	BWL	4
Post-doc	11	Social Sciences	24
PhD Student	25	Humanities	16
Other	7	WIM	4
		UMA Strategy	3
		External	9

Support and Services

Dimension Criteria

Number of consultations including target groups and thematic scope

Satisfaction of researchers with consultations

Outcomes and success of Open Science Grants, outcomes and feedback

The Open Science Office **has provided over 60 Open Science consultations since the beginning of 2022**, supporting researchers at the university with integrating Open Science into their research:

Support and Services

Dimension Criteria

Number of consultations including target groups and thematic scope

Satisfaction of researchers with consultations

Outcomes and success of Open Science Grants, outcomes and feedback

In the experience of the Open Science Office the consultations always came to a **positive conclusion**:

Case Study 2: Junior Professor, Economic History, BW Stiftung Funding Application:

“Many thanks for these really useful edits and comments! I’ve incorporated the changes you suggest and the proposal is now a lot stronger.”

Case Study 3: PhD Student, Social Sciences, Open Access

“I am very happy with the extremely helpful service of the Open Science Office. They responded very quick and answered all my questions related to copyright issues in detail.”

Support and Services

Dimension Criteria

Number of consultations including target groups and thematic scope

Satisfaction of researchers with consultations

Outcomes and success of Open Science Grants, outcomes and feedback

In two rounds (2021; 2022) of **funding** the Open Science Office has awarded just under **50,000 EURs to 12 projects (out of 36 applications):**

Support and Services

Dimension Criteria

Number of consultations including target groups and thematic scope

Satisfaction of researchers with consultations

Outcomes and success of Open Science Grants, outcomes and feedback

Six projects are now finished, and they alone have provided over 100 deliverables related to Open Science Practices:

Open Science Deliverable	No. of Deliverables
Open Data	9
Open Code	4
Open Materials	8
Pre-registration	10
Registered Report	0
Open Access Publications	3
Conference Presentations	11
Conference Posters	2

One grant produced **18 new open Educational Resources**
[Mannheim Open Science Meetup](#) provided **over 50 events**

Support and Services

Dimension Criteria

Number of consultations including target groups and thematic scope

Satisfaction of researchers with consultations

Outcomes and success of Open Science Grants, outcomes and feedback

The Open Science Grants were presented at a European conference, the Open Science FAIR 2023, and were reviewed very positively:

“It is extremely valuable that the institution specifically supports and encourages research evaluation processes related to open science. All participants should see this example.” - Reviewer 1

This review is also reflected positively in the awardees experiences as well:

“I think that this format of an Open Science Grant is an excellent way to help junior researchers gain some independence, and by the same token, to get open science practices in the daily routine of the next generation of researchers.” - 2021 Grant Awardee

Networking and Visibility

Impact Report, Section 4.3

Networking and Visibility

Dimension Criteria

Networking within the university, regionally, nationally or internationally

Organisation of public events

Presentation of the Open Science Office at national and international events

The Open Science Office has worked extensively with likeminded partners to expand accessibility and visibility of Open Science:

Division I

Networking and Visibility

Dimension Criteria

Networking within the university, regionally, nationally or internationally

Organisation of public events

Presentation of the Open Science Office at national and international events

The Open Science Office has organised the following large scale public events:

- Open Science Day 2021; 2022; 2023

- Trifels Summer School on Open Science in 2022

Networking and Visibility

Dimension Criteria

Networking within the university, regionally, nationally or internationally

Organisation of public events

Presentation of the Open Science Office at national and international events

8. BIBLIOTHEKSKONGRESS LEIPZIG 2022:

Kongress & Fachausstellung: [#FreiräumeSchaffen](#)
31. Mai – 02. Juni 2022

Future Directions and Summary

Future Directions

1. Continuation of the existing portfolio:

Training & Education

Support & Services

Networking

2. Further Planned Developments

Curricular Integration

Guidelines

Subject-specific requirements

E.g. new **Mannheim Masters in Social Data Science** includes a compulsory ***“Open and Reproducible Research”*** module led by the Open Science Office from 2024 onwards.

To ensure the sustainability the consultation service the Open Science Office will continue to **expand guidance centrally on the university website**

Intensify communication with departments of less represented subjects.

Summary of Open Science Office Impact Report 2021-2023

Dimensions

Training & Education

Support & Services

Networking

The Open Science Office has provided over 70 hours of training and educational opportunities to almost 600 individuals since 2021.

Summary of Open Science Office Impact Report 2021-2023

Dimensions

Training & Education

Support & Services

Networking

The Open Science Office has provided over 70 hours of training and educational opportunities to almost 600 individuals since 2021.

Beyond training and education, the Open Science Office has provided over 60 Open Science consultations since 2022

12 projects have been awarded Open Science Grants and of the 6 that have been completed, over 100 deliverables have been produced.

Summary of Open Science Office Impact Report 2021-2023

Dimensions

Training & Education

Support & Services

Networking

The Open Science Office has provided over 70 hours of training and educational opportunities to almost 600 individuals since 2021.

Beyond training and education, the Open Science Office has provided over 60 Open Science consultations since 2022

12 projects have been awarded Open Science Grants and of the 6 that have been completed, over 100 deliverables have been produced.

The university's approach has been presented at 6 conferences and 3 publications have been written while simultaneously working with administrative and research departments within the university.

Summary of Open Science Office Impact Report 2021-2023

Dimensions

Training & Education

Support & Services

Networking

The Open Science Office has provided over 70 hours of training and educational opportunities to almost 600 individuals.

Beyond the Open Science Office, since 2021, 12 publications and 12 presentations have been delivered.

The university's approach has been presented at 6 conferences and 3 publications have been written while simultaneously working with administrative and research departments within the university.

Overall, the Open Science Office achieved *impact in all evaluation dimensions*. It implements and advances the strategic goals of the University of Mannheim regarding Open Science.